

FAIR Implementation Framework

for Repositories and Data Service Providers

To support the adoption and implementation of existing and emerging tools, methods and resources, FAIR-IMPACT has developed the FAIR Implementation Framework (FIF)¹ to help different stakeholders assess their drivers for becoming (more) FAIR-enabling and their current practices so that they can develop realistic action and engagement plans to implement FAIR.

The framework illustrates that while the implementation of specific tools and methods is crucial for enabling FAIR, it is equally important to consider other factors that will impact on the overall success of FAIR-enabling efforts. To this end, the FAIR Implementation Framework adapts the approach introduced by the ACME-FAIR methodology² which places an equal emphasis on assessing capabilities for enabling FAIR and on active engagement to ensure uptake of FAIR-enabling practices.

The FAIR Implementation Framework

¹ <https://fair-impact.eu/fair-implementation-framework>

² <https://zenodo.org/communities/acme-fair/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest>

This document will show the different instruments that were developed in FAIR-IMPACT to implement the FAIR Implementation Framework for Repositories and Data Service Providers specifically. This was done in the context of the two rounds of support programmes that were organised for this stakeholder group.

Instructions will be given on how the instruments should be used and what their purposes are. Additional tips and suggestions are also included. It is recommended to use all the instruments together and follow the full series of steps of the FAIR Implementation Framework, but each instrument can also be used on its own. Each instrument is packaged with the relevant materials and information alongside it. By making these instruments publicly available, we hope to support more Repositories and Data Service Providers on their journey towards becoming more FAIR-enabling.

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Consider your drivers

The first step of the FAIR Implementation Framework is to consider your drivers for becoming (more) FAIR-enabling. Identifying which specific drivers are most important to the repository or data service provider will help to create focus throughout the rest of the framework steps. To create a useful and actionable FAIR Implementation Action Plan later on, it is important to define boundaries of your scope and to choose specific elements to put your attention to.

Working on this topic also helps a team of diverse employees or stakeholders make explicit their ideas and opinions, which are often only implicit and can differ between individuals with unique perspectives on the organisation. This helps develop a unified perspective on what objectives the organisation as a whole should strive towards.

To this end, a support instrument was developed to allow different drivers to be evaluated and scored. The results of the instrument can be used as a compass to navigate the next steps in the framework.

In the 'Consider Your Drivers' support instrument, three clusters of drivers are evaluated:

- **Serving Depositors**
- **Serving Reusers**
- **Serving your Organisation**

Each cluster consists of multiple different drivers, which are to be scored on a scale of 1-5, where scores correspond to:

1. **Not a driver**
2. **Slight driver**
3. **Moderate driver**
4. **Strong driver**
5. **Very strong driver**

Each statement should be scored to gain the most complete insight into your drivers. It is important to assign the scores realistically, and not base your answers on social desirability. No organisation can find all statements equally important or work on them all at the same time. Moreover, to develop a feasible FAIR Implementation Action Plan later on it is important to make choices and narrow your scope now. Being honest and diverse in your scoring will help you later on to set priorities and define the objectives that are most important to invest effort in.

Enter your score: 1. Not a driver 2. Slight driver 3. Moderate driver 4. Strong driver 5. Very strong driver	Drivers: Serving Depositors
0	Our data service should provide researchers the means to store and share digital research objects, according to the FAIR principles.
0	Our data service should be a service that is <i>*trusted*</i> by our community of users.
0	Our data service should provide <i>*appropriate access levels*</i> for (sensitive) research objects
0	Our data service should provide <i>*long-term access*</i> to research outputs
0	Our data service should facilitate depositors to <i>*comply with requirements*</i> posed by funders, publishers or legal obligations.
0	Our data service should facilitate users to comply with <i>*international (community) standards*</i> .

Enter your score: 1. Not a driver 2. Slight driver 3. Moderate driver 4. Strong driver 5. Very strong driver	Drivers: Serving Reusers
0	Our data service aims to make digital research objects available to <i>*as large an audience*</i> as possible
0	Our data service and research objects should be easily findable and accessible <i>*for people*</i> .
0	Our data service wants to increase the <i>*machine-actionability*</i> of research objects.
0	Our data service should make it easy to use research objects to <i>*reproduce and verify research findings*</i>
0	Our data service wants to <i>*stimulate reuse*</i> of digital research objects to address novel research questions

Enter your score: 1. Not a driver 2. Slight driver 3. Moderate driver 4. Strong driver 5. Very strong driver	Drivers - Serving your Organisation
0	Our data service strives to be (one of the) main infrastructures for researchers to <i>*share*</i> research objects.
0	Our data service strives to be (one of the) main infrastructures for researchers for the <i>*reuse*</i> of research objects.
0	Our data service should be recognized as a key-stakeholder in the <i>*national science landscape*</i>
0	Our data service should be recognized as a key-stakeholder in the <i>*international science landscape*</i>
0	Our data service should have insight into the <i>*level of FAIRness*</i> of our digital objects.
0	Our data service wants to make <i>*better connections*</i> to other services, such as the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC).
0	Our data service wants to make our community of users more <i>*aware of our FAIR-enabling qualities and practices*</i> .

The three clusters of Drivers in the instrument

The instrument also includes a visualisation tab, where the evaluated drivers are presented to provide explicit insight into where the focus of the Repository or Data Service Provider lies. This information can then be taken along to the next step in the Framework.

Example visualisation the instrument provides. This hypothetical repository seems to focus mostly on ‘Serving Depositors’.

Navigate to or reference this instrument:

Brinkman, L., Verburg, M., Grootveld, M., Boerman, S., & Thorpe, D. E. (2025). Consider Your Drivers - A FAIR-IMPACT instrument. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15471797>

Assessing your capabilities

After identifying your drivers for becoming (more) FAIR-enabling, the second step in the FAIR Implementation Framework is to assess your current capabilities. The results of these two steps together will be able to help you inform your scope of action.

Next to your chosen area(s) of focus (drivers), it is important to evaluate the capabilities you have to implement action in those areas. This step not only focuses on the current capabilities, but also asks you to consider your desired future level of capability in specific areas. This way, you can formulate the gap between these two elements, and identify necessary actions to bridge this.

Assessing your capabilities can also help you to identify what is within your sphere of influence to change within your organisation, which will lead to you defining implementable actions. If you learn you are lacking capabilities in an area of focus which is very important to you, you may consider onboarding an additional team member who is able to provide those capabilities, or you may identify stakeholders you need to engage with to increase the chances of your actions being effectively implemented (we consider stakeholder engagement in Step 4 of the framework).

In the 'Assessing your Capabilities' support instrument, five different FAIR-enabling aspects are considered:

- **Policy**
- **FAIR data assessment**
- **Supporting the FAIRness of objects**
- **Displaying trustworthiness**
- **Engaging with your community**

For each topic one or more questions are compiled, based on existing materials, such as Assessing Capability Maturity and Engagement with FAIR-enabling Practices (ACME-FAIR)³. Questions are either a checkbox or a levels-based selection question. For each question, you first consider what currently best describes the situation of your organisation. Next, you consider what you aspire to achieve on this topic. These are aspirational plans to improve certain FAIR-enabling aspects.

Assess your current capabilities

- How aware are you about the FAIR principles?
- How fair-enabling are your practices currently?
- What FAIR-enabling services and support do you currently provide?
- What are the gaps in the FAIR-enabling services?

³ Joy Davidson, Angus Whyte, Laura Molloy, Marjan Grootveld, & Mark Thorley. (2022). Defining the Policy Environment: ACME-FAIR Issue #1 (2.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6345332>

4. Displaying trustworthiness					
<p>For potential users to make informed decisions about how they interact with repositories and data service providers, it is important that they can develop a sense of trust in the service and organisation. To this end, it is important for the service provider to display their trustworthiness clearly and transparently to the outside world, ideally in a way that both humans and machines can understand.</p> <p>The checklist for this topic consists of a selection of CoreTrustSeal requirements for trustworthy data repositories⁵. CoreTrustSeal offers a certification service, but organisations can also use the requirements and guidance internally, without (yet) aiming for certification. Not all service providers are in scope for CoreTrustSeal certification, so not all requirements may be applicable to your organisation. This does not mean the organisation is less trustworthy, as long as it is clearly communicated which practices are and are not to be expected from the organisation and why. Transparency is key.</p>					
<p>➔ 4a. Continuity of service: We have a plan to ensure ongoing access to and preservation of data and metadata. [CTS R3]</p>				<i>Current</i>	<i>Aspiration</i>
Level 0	Level 1	Level 2	Level 3	<i>Selected level:</i>	<i>Selected level:</i>
No, we have not considered this	To some extent (e.g., we are currently discussing potential implementation, or are drafting a plan)	We have considered this and implemented it to the extent that is relevant to our organisation (e.g., a fully documented plan, or clearly supported decision to not have such a plan)	Level 3 + We have clearly and publicly communicated this to potential users (e.g., provided a link or statement on our website)	<i>Evidence:</i>	<i>Reasoning:</i>

Example of one of the questions in the instrument

To ensure you are able to develop a focused and feasible FAIR Implementation Action Plan, it is recommended to consider which aspects are important for you to improve on immediately or on the relatively short term. Moreover, it is important to keep your identified drivers for change in mind as well. This way, you can select some areas in which improvement is deemed important, whereas other topics can remain at the same level as your current capabilities when direct change is not prioritised. Much like in the Drivers exercise, it is important to set a scope for your desired changes and allow some topics to be considered less important at the moment. Know that you can always revisit these instruments when you are advancing in certain areas to consider the topics once more and potentially update your plans to incorporate new goals in different areas.

The source materials for the questions in the instrument are all linked, so you can already start exploring these tools to learn more about relevant aspects if desired.

After filling in this instrument, you can now take the next step to create your FAIR Implementation Action Plan. Keeping your filled in Drivers and Capabilities instruments with you will help you prioritise your goals and activities.

Navigate to or reference this instrument:

Grootveld, M., Verburg, M., Brinkman, L., & Thorpe, D. E. (2025). Assessing Your Capabilities - A FAIR-IMPACT instrument. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15471970>

Creating a FAIR Implementation Action Plan

After evaluating the Drivers for change that are important to your organisation and the desires for improving certain FAIR-enabling Capabilities, everything is now in place to start the creation of the FAIR Implementation Action Plan. In this Action Plan, you specify the objectives you have and break these down into concrete actions that will lead you to achieving these goals.

The instrument developed to help you create this FAIR Implementation Action Plan offers a structured way to plan your actions and ensure these remain linked to your original intentions. The spreadsheet style instrument is intended to be continually used, reviewed, and updated, as will be explained in a later step.

Keeping in mind the Drivers that you have identified as most important to the organisation, as well as the capabilities you want to improve, you can derive one or more objectives that are currently the most important for your organisation to work towards. The instrument first asks you to reiterate the Drivers and Capabilities identified as most important, to keep these at the top of the Action Plan at all times.

Next, you specify your objective. This can be a bit more broad and aspirational, but should be meaningful and feasible to achieve. For this objective, you specify the related aspects and results of the previous instruments. It is possible to work on multiple objectives at the same time in your plan, or to have your objectives specified for different timelines, but it is recommended to focus on one objective at a time while drafting the Action Plan. So before you create more objectives, first have a look at how your first objective can be broken down into specific and granular actions.

It will generally take more than one action to achieve an objective. Therefore, the instrument suggests you label your actions to keep them clearly separated. Next, you describe your action as clearly as possible. To check whether actions are feasible and get a sense of the amount of work it will take, it is recommended to associate specific milestones and/or performance indicators with each action (e.g. if your action is “Test our datasets on FAIRness”, an associated KPI could be “30 datasets tested”).

For a clear timeline, you associate dates and deadlines with the action. Here you also start to apply an order to your actions and identify what action needs to be done before another action can be started. Ordering your actions like this is also done by assigning them a priority. A high-level distinction is made in the instrument between ‘short-term’ and ‘longer-term’, but it is recommended to specify such terms in a way that is relevant to your organisation (e.g. short-term could mean ‘one week’ or ‘6 months’ or anything in between, depending on the general pace of your organisation and the granularity of the action). The more attention you pay to this part of the planning, the more clarity you will have about when there will be a lot of work to be done at the same time. Maybe some deadlines can already

be moved to ensure the feasibility of the plan and a clear match to the available people and effort over time.

Each action needs at least one person assigned to it to have responsibility on its completion. Some actions may have multiple people associated with it as it requires some form of collaboration. Therefore, the instrument asks you to detail who is involved and what the related responsibilities are for each person.

Lastly, the instrument includes a simple progress tracker, which can be used to communicate progress or identified issues that need to be discussed with others.

Altogether, this instrument offers a structured way to plan activities towards a central objective. It is important that the structure of the plan fits well into the way of working already established in your organisation. It is therefore offered as a flexible instrument that can also be adapted to individual needs or to move to different formats or platforms.

FAIR Implementation Action Plan - Repositories and Data Services			
Organisation		Organisation name	
Main driver(s)		Please indicate your results from the 'Consider your Drivers' tool. Which drivers are most important to your organisation currently?	
Category focus		Please indicate your chosen area(s) of focus for improvement, as per the 'Capabilities self-assessment checklist' and/or other considerations. See the box on the right for a reminder of the categories.	
Instructions			
Fill in the Action Plan template by defining concrete granular actions that will help you advance towards your target. If you have chosen multiple objectives to achieve, you can copy and paste the rows below. This Action Plan should work for you. If you feel that making edits to the template will fit your needs better, then please do implement this.			
Objective #1	[Objective name]		
Category		Indicate the category the objective relates to primarily	
Related driver(s)		Provide the specific driver(s) this objective relates to	
Related capability assessment question(s)		Provide the specific capability self-assessment question(s) this objective relates to	
Current position		Indicate the current position scored in the capability self-assessment tool	
Target position		Indicate the target position scored in the capability self-assessment tool	
Action #	Actions	Milestones and/or KPIs	Dates
Recommended to label actions with reference to objective number (#1.1, #1.2, etc.)	Describe one specific action per row that is required to meet the objective	Provide any milestones and or KPIs that will help you measure progress on this action. You can choose which formulation you are most comfortable with, but do make sure that they are formulated effectively (e.g. SMART)	Provide deadlines for each to be completed (dd-mm-yy)

Part of the FAIR Implementation Action Plan instrument

Some important tips for creating a good Action Plan are:

- An objective needs to be able to be tested in a sensitive way. While they may be quite aspirational and big goals, they need to be able to be captured in a set of actions. If there is no way to identify how an objective would be achieved, there is no way to meaningfully work towards it.
- An objective works best when it is written in a positive, active, and affirmative way. Don't focus on what you will no longer do, but focus on what you will now do instead.
- As we touched upon in the Assessing Your Capabilities section already: Your organisation must be in control of achieving the objective. There are many things that

we wish we could change that are (partly) outside our control. If you cannot control when an objective is achieved, it should not be in your Action Plan (but maybe you can invite some other organisation to put it on their Action Plan!)

- Keep in mind that engaging with (external) stakeholder is an important element of many actions, and needing to involve stakeholders does not mean the objective is outside of your control.
- The objective also should make sense for the organisation. This should come out of the Drivers and Capabilities instruments already, but it is important to be aware of the organisation's mission for the future and make sure the objectives align with that.
- Another possibly strange, but nonetheless important, question to ask when designing objectives is: "Is there a better reason *not* to achieve the objective?" This could be because it is not the main focus or mission of the organisation, or because there are ongoing developments that will impair or otherwise impact the objective.
- When designing objectives, it is important to have some certainty that the organisation supports this objective, especially when there are costs involved. Is the organisation willing to 'pay' for reaching an objective, in money or other resources like investing employee time. If some level of organisational buy-in isn't established, there is a risk of work being halted halfway through because priorities are shifted. Knowing the effort you have available to spend on specific topics can help you design feasible actions and a plan that will get completed.
- To make an objective achievable, it needs to be well defined. In the instrument, we do this by breaking it down into actions which are well thought out and planned.
- An action must have a deadline, even if this deadline has to shift to accommodate changes. An action without a deadline will often not get achieved and likely is not so relevant to the objective.

Now that there is a first draft of the FAIR Implementation Action Plan, you can enrich this with a Stakeholder Engagement Strategy in the next step of the Framework.

Navigate to or reference this instrument:

Verburg, M., Grootveld, M., Brinkman, L., Grau, N., & Massol, M. (2025). FAIR Implementation Action Plan - a FAIR-IMPACT instrument. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15471978>

Developing a Stakeholder Engagement Strategy

Different actions that have been defined in your FAIR Implementation Action Plan will likely include other stakeholders in some way. For example, you may need a colleague with certain expertise to assist in achieving a certain goal, need support from management to pursue a certain objective, or need interactions with your users or other important stakeholders to shape envisioned innovations. To this end, an instrument was developed that enhances the FAIR Implementation Action Plan by creating a Stakeholder Engagement Strategy.

Engage with relevant stakeholders to ensure uptake

- Consider how you will work with different stakeholders to identify needs and requirements
- Consider how you will make sure that all relevant actors know what they need to do and when
- Consider how you will build the necessary capacity among the different actors
- Develop an engagement strategy

The Stakeholder Engagement Strategy instrument comprises a spreadsheet with the following column headings to help you create your strategy:

Stakeholder group: identify the stakeholders that are relevant to your actions and objectives. Example stakeholders are provided, but these can be modified and/or additional stakeholder groups can be added.

Interest and influence of this stakeholder group for your action plan?: select the level of interest and influence of the stakeholder group for your actions and objectives.⁴

Which thematic area(s) are relevant to this stakeholder: a free text field to enter which thematic areas relating to implementing FAIR might be relevant to this stakeholder. The following examples are given: 'Policy; Incentives; Community; Training & Support; Infrastructure; Other (please specify)'

What do you want to get out of your interaction with this stakeholder?: A free text field to identify what your goal is in engaging with this stakeholder

What do you have to offer?: Think about what do you, as a repository or service provider have to offer to this stakeholder group. This is to encourage the engagement with the stakeholder(s) to be a two-way interaction and to better understand their incentives for engaging with your organisation in relation to your actions and objectives.

⁴ See the following link for an example of how to map stakeholders according to their level of interest and influence: Regional Laboratory on Urban Governance for Health and Well-being, Stakeholder Analysis and Mapping:
<https://web.archive.org/web/20250205085327/https://ughw.org/stakeholder-mapping-analysis-project/>

Ways to interact with stakeholder: identify here any key communication channels to engage with this stakeholder. Who are the key persons?

Priority: is engagement with this stakeholder group a high, medium or low priority?

Stakeholder group	Interest and influence of this stakeholder group for your action plan?	Which thematic area(s) are relevant to this stakeholder: Policy; Incentives; Community; Training & Support; Infrastructure; Other (please specify)	What do you want to get out of your interaction with this stakeholder?
Archivists			
Technical Staff			
Researchers as data providers			
Researchers as data reusers			
Research data supporters			
Institutional leaders			
Funders and data policy makers			
Journal publishers			
[Please add others where relevant]			

Part of the Stakeholder Engagement Strategy instrument

By filling in these different questions and aspects, you will enrich your Action Plan and the specific objectives and actions defined. Explicitly considering stakeholder engagement like this can make your Action Plan more feasible, as implementing actions to engage stakeholders can be included as their own actions on the path of realising your objective.

Experiences from the participants of the FAIR-IMPACT Support Programmes have shown that engagement with stakeholders is often the most complicating factor in an Action Plan. Externals often cause delays of timelines and deadlines, and can also complicate the achievement of objectives by presenting new challenges or contradicting opinions. Taking stakeholder engagement into account from the start of the Action Plan creation can help create clarity on how complex objectives will be to achieve. Generally speaking, the more stakeholders involved, the more complex the objective will be.

The Stakeholder Engagement strategy instrument is enriched with experiences and advice from the Digital Repository of Ireland, which is included in the published record.

Navigate to or reference this instrument:

Brinkman, L., Thorpe, D. E., Horton, L., Griffith, L., & Verburg, M. (2025). Developing a Stakeholder Engagement Strategy - A FAIR-IMPACT instrument. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15471805>

Continuing your FAIR-enabling journey

The last steps of the FAIR Implementation Framework show how you can continue your FAIR-enabling journey after you have completed your first Action Plan draft.

First, some actions you have included in your Plan may require you to learn about new topics or improve existing skills and knowledge. One of the steps towards achieving such goals is then to look for relevant tools, methods, and approaches, and existing training materials, to add as intermediate steps in the Plan. For example, if you want to learn more about certification, you may add as an action that you first read the CoreTrustSeal Requirements and other available materials to improve your knowledge on the topic. Or maybe you revisit some of the resources linked in the Assessing your Capabilities instrument.

FAIR-IMPACT created a Catalogue of Resources⁵ to support the practical implementation of FAIR-enabling practices by sharing relevant resources with the community. This curated set of resources can be browsed to identify which tools, methods, or approaches are the right fit for you.

After enriching your FAIR Implementation Action Plan with intermediary actions and resources, you will be able to start the implementation of your Plan. It is essential for the continued relevance and success of your Plan to regularly review your progress and refine the Plan where needed. Maybe some initial deadlines were a bit too tight, or maybe your explorations have led you to include additional actions on your way to the main objective. Your Plan is meant to be dynamic, as it needs to be able to respond to real life circumstances and remain feasible for you to pursue. Once you have achieved a certain objective, you can start specifying a new one, for example by going back to Step 1 of the Framework and working your way through your current drivers and capabilities once more.

The last step of the FAIR Implementation Framework considers the sharing of your experiences. Learning from others is one of the most useful ways to improve your FAIR-enabling qualities, and therefore contributing your own experiences to the community will help others do the same. What did you work on? What worked well? What could be done differently in the future? What resources and tools worked well for you? Consider writing a blog or presenting your experiences to disseminate this throughout the community. You can

⁵ <https://catalogue.fair-impact.eu/>

share things with your own colleagues, other involved stakeholders like your depositors, or other repositories and stakeholders in the wider ecosystem.

FAIR-IMPACT shared such experiences by writing up FAIR Implementation Stories⁶ from each participant that received support throughout the project. These stories can show others what these different organisations and individuals worked on, what lessons they learned, and what others can learn from that in the future. These kinds of dissemination activities showcase the work you put in with the creation and implementation of (parts of) your FAIR Implementation Action Plan, and are valuable resources for others looking to do the same. They can also be a way to establish connections with others working on similar topics or encountering similar challenges, allowing you to work together to advance. Dissemination therefore does not have to wait until all your objectives have been achieved, but can also concern very specific or granular actions you have taken in between. The journey towards FAIR is ever ongoing, so do not wait to celebrate and share your experiences in the meantime!

Sharing your experiences is the last step of the FAIR Implementation Framework, but as has been emphasised before, the intention is that your Action Plan and implementation work continues dynamically, where you hop back and forth along the steps of the Framework to advance on certain goals, add new ones, and continuously progress on your FAIR-enabling journey.

⁶ <https://fair-impact.eu/implementation-adoption-stories>